

Bernoulli's Number One Solution for Stochastic Equilibrium

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Abstract

The present research studies the numerical methods for resolving Bernoulli's divisive statistical stability, because it is difficult to find analytical solutions for the largest number of stochastic divisive calculations. We found a new way for Bernoulli by adding white noise. Price measurement was achieved with a variety of selected models, and we realized through the solutions that the larger the (n) we find, the more we find the direct solution that approaches zero, and the error rate that approaches zero. The difference between a numerical solution and a direct solution has been observed.

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1. Introduction:

Bernoulli's principle is an important theory in fluid mechanics; it involves a lot of knowledge of fluid mechanics, and is Daniel Bernoulli (D. Bernoulli, Swiss physicists, mathematicians, 1700~1782) in 1726, is three basic equation of hydrodynamics another. It is the embodiment of objects mechanical energy conversion of hydraulic .Bernoulli equation solves the problem of force and energy which is often involved in engineering practice, which lays the theoretical foundation for solving hydraulic calculation of actual engineering. The application of this equation runs through the course of hydraulic mechanics. Based on the principle of Bernoulli's equation, this paper summarizes the research status of its application at home and abroad and provides direction for the future application of the Bernoulli equation which is one of the central objects of present-day control theory. In fact, in the theory of control systems, the qualitative control problem has received considerable research interest. This problem is regarded as an extension of the classical result (Venkatarama, 2006). (Platen, 1999) on controllability and stability of linear systems which is relevant to such differential equations, see (Carletti, 2006; Cao & Pope, 2003; Fleury, 2006; Higham, 2000; Bernard & Fleury, 2001; Evans, 2006). Bernoulli differential equations also play predominant roles in other control theory problems such as dynamic games, linear systems with Markovian jumps, and stochastic control. The study of such differential equations, which also appears in some other areas such as biomathematics and multidimensional transport processes, is an interesting area of the current research. There exists a rather extensive literature on the Bernoulli differential equation, mainly developed within the automatic control literature. We refer the readers to (Higham, 2000) as an extensive survey as well as to (Carletti, 2006; Cao & Pope, 2003; Fleury, 2006; Stirzaker, 2005; Kloeden & Platen, 1999) as fundamental papers on this area. In our work, we study the Stability analysis of the stochastic Bernoulli differential equation, which has the form:-

$$y' + p(x)y + b(x)w_t = h(x)y^n ; x \in [0, T] \quad \dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

Where the functions $p(x)$, $b(x)$ are continuous in x . Moreover, $h(x)$ is a function that is defined on the same interval and w_t is a white noise process. And $n \neq 1$.

2. Main Results:

In this section, we can state and prove a theorem by using a numerical stochastic differential equation.

Theorem1:

Suppose that $y' + p(x)y + b(x)w_t = h(x)y^n ; x \in [0, T]$. Where the functions $p(x)$, $q(x)$ and $h(x)$ are continuous in x . And w_t is a white noise process, then:

$$Y_{n+1} = \left[y(\tau_n) + p(\tau_n)(\tau_{n+1} - \tau_n) - r(\tau_n)(w_{\tau_{n+1}} - w_{\tau_n})^2 \right] * I. f \quad \dots \text{Equation (2)}$$

For $n=0, 1, 2, \dots, N-1$; with initial value $Y_0 = X_0$. Where I. f is integrating factor.

Proof:

Assume that $z = y^{1-n}$, of the Bernoulli equation (1) is known

then $dz = (1 - n)y^{-n}$

$$\left\{ \frac{dz}{dx} = (1 - n) y^{-n} \frac{dy}{dx} \right\} \div (1 - n)$$

Becomes:

$$\left(\frac{1}{1-n}\right) \frac{dz}{dx} + y^{-n} \frac{dy}{dx} \quad \dots \text{Equation (3)}$$

from equation (3) in equation (1), we get:

$$\left(\frac{1}{1-n}\right) \frac{dz}{dx} + p(x) z + b(x) \frac{dw}{dx} y^{-n} = Q(x) \quad \dots \text{Equation (4)}$$

and we also let:

$$z_1 = y^n \text{ then } dz = y^n dw$$

$$\frac{dz_1}{dx} = y^{-n} \frac{dw}{dx} \quad \dots \text{Equation (5)}$$

from equation (5) in equation (4), we get:

$$\left(\frac{1}{1-n}\right) \frac{dz}{dx} + p(x) z + b(x) \frac{dz_1}{dx} = Q(x)$$

$$\frac{dz}{dx} + (1-n) p(x)z + (1-n) b(x) \frac{dz_1}{dx} = (1-n) Q(x)$$

$$dz + (1-n) p(x)z dx + (1-n) b(x) dz_1 = (1-n) Q(x) dx$$

$$dz + (1-n) p(x)z dx = -(1-n) b(x) dz_1 + (1-n) Q(x) dx$$

let:

$$k(x) = -(1-n) b(x) dz_1 + (1-n) Q(x) dx$$

then we get:

$$dz + (1-n) p(x)z dx = k(x)$$

and

$$I. f = e^{\int p(x) dx}$$

and the G.S is:

$$Z. I. f = \int I. f k(x) dx$$

Where initial value $z_{t_0} = z_0$ subdivide the interval $[t_0, T]$ into N-subintervals according to the following discretization

$$t_0 = \tau_0 < \tau_1 < \dots < \tau_n < \dots < \tau_N = T$$

The Bernoulli approximation is defined as a continuous time stochastic process

$Y = \{ Y(t), t_0 \leq t \leq T \}$ Satisfying the iterative scheme:

$$Y_{n+1} = \left[y(\tau_n) + p(\tau_n)(\tau_{n+1} - \tau_n) - r(\tau_n)(w_{\tau_{n+1}} - w_{\tau_n})^2 \right] * I. f \quad \dots \text{Equation (6)}$$

for $n=0,1,2,\dots,N-1$; with initial value $Y_0 = X_0$.

Illustration (I):

Consider:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} dx &= p(t)xdt - R(t) x dw \\ x(0) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

then the unique solution is:

$$x(t) = e^{q(t) - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t p^2(s) ds + \int_0^t R(s) dw}, \text{ for } 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

where $p(t) = \mu \cos t$; $R(t) = \sin t$; $q(t) = \exp(t)$; $Y_0 = 0$. ; As discussed previously in illustration (I), the following tables (A, B and C) is needed for error exact and as follows:

Table (A) Exact solution by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Exact at the final time
1	2^5	1.0601
	2^6	1.4228
	2^8	1.0520
	2^9	1.3575
	2^{10}	1.3852
	2^{11}	1.0125

Table (B) Numerical solution by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Numerical at the final time
1	2^5	0.4636
	2^6	0.4596
	2^8	0.4541
	2^9	0.6079
	2^{10}	0.6189
	2^{11}	0.4441

Figure (1) exact solution and the numerical solution by Bernoulli scheme with $N = 2^{11}$; $R = 1$

Table (C) Error generated by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Error at the final time
1	2^5	0.6528
	2^6	0.9792
	2^8	0.6079
	2^9	0.8975
	2^{10}	0.7987
	2^{11}	0.5489

Figure (1.1) Absolute error between the numerical solution and exact solution with $N = 2^{11}$; $R = 1$

Another example of Illustration. (With Absolute Error Test and Comparisons):

That is:-

$$\left. \begin{aligned} dx &= \mu x dt - R(t)x dw \\ x(0) &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

The unique solution is:

$$x(t) = e^{\int_0^t \mu^2(s) ds + \int_0^t R(s) dw}, \text{ for } 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

where: $R(t) = \sin t$; $\mu = 0.25$; $x_0 = 1$; $Y_0 = 0$; As discussed previously in illustration (II), the following table (D) is needed for error analysis and as follows:

Table (D) Exact solution by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Exact at the final time
1	2^8	0.7693
	2^9	0.9929

Table (E) Numerical solution by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Numerical at the final time
1	2^8	0.5692
	2^9	0.6125

Figure (2) exact solution and the numerical solution by Bernoulli scheme with $N = 2^8$; $R = 1$

Table (F) Error generated by the Bernoulli scheme

R Step size	N (discretized)	Error at the final time
1	2^8	0.2001
	2^9	0.3804

Figure (2.1) Absolute error between the Numerical solution and exact solution with $N = 2^8$; $R = 1$

3. Numerical Steps of Linear Stability for BM:

1. The concepts of strong and weak convergence concern the accuracy of numerical methods over a finite interval $[0, T]$, for a small step, sizes Δt . However, in many applications, the long-term, $t \rightarrow \infty$, behavior of an SDE is of interest.

2. Convergence bounds of the form:

$$E|X_n - X(T)| \leq C\Delta t^\gamma \text{ or } |E p(X_n) - E p(X(T))| \leq C\Delta t^\gamma$$

are not relevant in this context, since generally, the constant C grows unboundedly with T .

3. We return to the linear SDE:

$$dX(t) = [(p(t)x)dt + \mu(X(t)) dW(t)] * I. f, X(0) = X_0 \quad \dots \text{Equation (7)}$$

Where the function of RSDE allowed to be complex in the case where $\mu = 0$ and X_0 is constant, equation (7) reduces to the deterministic linear test equation, if we use the term

stable to mean that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} X(t) = 0$, for any X_0 . Then we see that stability is characterized by $R\{\lambda\} < 0$.

4. We will consider the two most common measures of stability; Mean-Square and Asymptotic (Bernard & Fleury, 2001). Assuming that $X_0 \neq 0$ with probability 1, solutions of SIDE is:

$$dX(t) = ((-2p(t) u(t) - q(t))z - p(t)) dt + \mu X(t) dW(t), X(0) = X_0$$

Satisfying:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} EX^2(t) = 0 \Leftrightarrow R\{\int_{t_0}^t \lambda\} + \frac{1}{2} |\mu|^2 < 0 \quad \dots \text{Equation (8)}$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |X(t)| = 0 \text{ with probability } 1 \Leftrightarrow R\{\int_{t_0}^t \lambda - \frac{1}{2} \mu^2\} < 0 \quad \dots \text{Equation (9)}$$

The left-hand side of equation (8) defines what is meant by mean-square stability. The right-hand side of equation (8) completely characterizes this property in terms of the function SDE. Similarly, equation (9) defines and characterizes asymptotic stability.

Consider the following example of Mean-Square stability:

$$dx = [(u(t) x)dt + g x dw] * I.f$$

$$x(0) = 1$$

where $g(t) = \cos t$; $T = 10$; $u(t) = \mu = 3000$; $X_0 = 1$; $\Delta t = 1, 2, 1/4$; and $N = T / \Delta t$; $0 \leq t \leq T$.

And asymptotic stability:

where $p(t) = \cos t$; $u(t) = g(t) = \sin t$; $T = 500$; $\Delta t = 1, 2, 1/4$; and $N = T / \Delta t$

The Figure (5) plots the sample average of $E(X^2)$ against t in this picture the $\Delta t = 1$ and $\Delta t = 1/2$ curves increase with t , while the $\Delta t = 1/4$ curve decays toward zero

Figure (5) Mean-Square and Asymptotic stability

4. Conclusions:

Numerical methods for solving stochastically determined differential equations are indispensable for analyzing stochastic phenomena. While exploring system characteristics that depend on trajectory-level attributes, powerful solvers are necessary. For strong

solvers, there are many methods, especially Bernoulli-type methods, although, for orders greater than 1, the complexity of these two methods will greatly increase. In many financial applications, the main emphasis is on the probability distribution of the solution, especially the mean and variance of the distribution. In this case, the weak solver may spice up. Away from stochastically determining the choice of differential equation solver, there is a variance reduction method that can improve computational efficiency. As long as statistical independence is maintained along the trajectory, pseudo-random numbers can be replaced with quasi-random analogs from low-variance sequences. In addition, the control variant provides another way to reduce variance and adds inefficient simulations that stochastically determine the trajectory of the differential equation.

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